

Fusion of Horizons: Search for New Paradigms in Inter-Religious Dialogue

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ABSTRACT

The FABC recommends the exercise of dialogue in three different areas of life in Asia: (i) dialogue with the Asian poor, (ii) intercultural dialogue and (iii) interreligious dialogue. Interreligious dialogue, which is the subject of our discussion, is classified into four types: Dialogue of life, Dialogue of action, Dialogue of theological exchange and Dialogue of religious experience. Employing the analytical and critical methodology, this paper aims at investigating various paradigms of interreligious dialogue that have been practiced down through the centuries, in view of developing a most feasible paradigm, based on the writings of Hans-Georg Gadamer. Accordingly, we have critically analysed the following models: (i) the ideal of both/and (Hegel), and (ii) the ideal of either/or (Kierkegaard), (iii) the metaphor of two books (Bonaventure), (iv) the intercultural hermeneutics (Schleiermacher and Gadamer), and (v) the fusion of horizons (Heidegger and Gadamer). Finally, our discussions boil down to Hans-Georg Gadamer's understanding of "fusion of horizons" and its implications in interreligious dialogue. According to Gadamer, "to acquire a horizon means that one learns to look beyond what is close at hand." A genuine fusion of horizons through dialogue always involves rising to a higher universality that overcomes our own particularity and that of the other. A fusion of horizons thus envisages respect for the differences of different religions. Here, one does not try to acquire mastery over the other and other religions based on our pre-judgments, rather strive to partake in the other and share the other's alterity. In order to foster interreligious dialogue as "fusion of horizons, we have to shun "ethnocentrism," and cultivate certain essential qualities like (i) openness to change, (ii) interreligious consciousness, and (iii) empathetic understanding. To conclude, the Pontifical Council for Interreligious Dialogue, in "Dialogue and Proclamation," advocates the people living in religious pluralistic societies to engage in meaningful dialogue for "the integral development and liberation of all people."

Keywords: Boundaries, Empathetic Understanding, Fusion of Horizons, Intercultural Hermeneutics, Interreligious Dialogue, Paradigms

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Introduction

The Federation of the Asian Bishops' Conference (FABC) recommends the exercise of dialogue in three different areas of life in Asia: (i) dialogue with the Asian poor; (ii) intercultural dialogue and (iii) interreligious dialogue. In the 1992 Plenary Session, the FABC very convincingly spelled out its role in the Asian Continent as "a Church that faithfully and lovingly witnesses to the Risen Lord Jesus and reaches out to the people of other faith and persuasions in effective dialogue of life [and dialogue of action] towards the integral liberation of all."¹

In the history of religions, "dialogue" about the meaning of beliefs, rituals, and ethics has no doubt been taking place, though informally and unrecorded, from the very beginning, or at least from the first encounter of divergent belief systems. However, the phrase "dialogue of religions" has become common in various religious traditions only since the second half of the twentieth century. Interreligious dialogue (IRD), a relatively new development in religious studies, is both lauded and feared by scholars and philosophers of religion. Some scholars praise interreligious dialogue as a method to foster greater respect, appreciation, and understanding between followers of different religions and faiths. But others consider interreligious dialogue to be a dangerous activity that transgresses the boundary between religious studies and theology.

The term "dialogue" is derived from the Greek words *logos* (translated as "word") and the prefix *dia* (translated as "through"). As Catherine Cornille observes, the term dialogue tends to be used to cover a wide range of engagements between religious traditions, from daily interaction between believers [...] to organized discussions and debates between expert scholars and from formal or casual exchanges between spiritual or institutional leaders to inter-religious activism around social issues."² Plato, for example, differentiated the concept of "dialogue" from other "conversations." He used the

term "dialogue" to pertain to conversations where "truth" was sought through the exchange of words. In Plato's own words: "It does not at all admit of verbal expression like other studies, but as a result of continued application to the subject itself and communion therewith, it is brought to birth in the soul on a sudden, as light that is kindled by a leaping spark, and thereafter it nourishes itself."³ In Indian philosophy, the Sanskrit word *samvada* (also spelled *samvad*) is commonly used to mean "dialogue" or "conversation" between two or more people."⁴ The Nyaya Sutras, in particular, advocate *samvada* as one of the sixteen categories leading to liberation⁵. For example, the Nyāya Sūtra, Verse 1.1.2, states that its purpose is to study and explain the application of more than sixteen categories of perfecting knowledge to attain liberation from wrong knowledge, faults, and sorrow: *duḥkha-janma-pravṛttidoṣa-mithyājñānānām uttarottarāpāye tadanantarā pāyāt apavargaḥ*.

Definitions of Interreligious Dialogue

Interreligious dialogue, simply stated, involves meeting people themselves and getting to know their religious traditions. Interreligious dialogue is "the interaction of mutual presence: speaking, listening, and witnessing the commitments, the values, the rituals of others."⁶ Perhaps the best definition of interreligious dialogue comes from John Taylor, who states, "Interreligious dialogue is a sustained conversation between parties who are not saying the same thing and who recognize and respect contradictions and mutual exclusions between their various ways of thinking."⁷ According to Cardinal Arinze,

3 Plato, *Epistles*, R. G. Bury, tr., in *Loeb Classical Library*, London, New York, 1929, VII, 531.

4 For example, *The Bhagavad-Gita*, 8: 70: *adhyesyate ca ya imam dharmyam samvādam āvayoh |jñāna-yajñena tenāham istah syām iti me matih. |* (One who studies our sacred "dialogue" will thereby worship Me through the sacrifice of transcendental knowledge. This is My opinion.)

5 A. Gautama, *Nyaya Sutras*, First Book: The Vada-marga is classified under sixteen steps: *Pramana, Prameya, Samsaya, Prayojana, Drshtanta, Sidhanta, Avayava, Tarka, Niranaya, Samvada, Jalpa, Vitanda, Hetvabhasa, Chala, Jati, and Nigrahaslhana*.

6 Paul Knitter, *Jesus and the Other Names*, New York: Orbis Books, 1996, 14.

7 John Taylor, "The Theological Basis of Interfaith Dialogue," in *Faith Meets Faith*, ed. Gerald Anderson and Thomas Stransky, Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1981, 94.

1 Cf. Franz-Josef Eilers, *For All the People of Asia*, Quezon City: Claretian Publications, 1997, 287.

2 Catherine Cornille, "Introduction," in *The Wiley-Blackwell Companion to Inter-religious Dialogue*, ed. Catherine Cornille, Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd., 2013, xii.

“Interreligious dialogue is a meeting of people of differing religions, in an atmosphere of freedom and openness, in order to listen to the other, to try to understand that person’s religion, and hopefully to seek possibilities of collaboration. It is hoped that the other partner will reciprocate because dialogue should be marked by a two-way and not a one-way movement.”⁸

In short, interreligious dialogue is a formal process in which authoritative members of at least two religious communities come together for an extended and serious discussion of the beliefs and practices that separate the communities. In light of the above definitions, we may argue that an interreligious dialogue requires four criteria: (i) interpersonal communication, (ii) different religious commitments, (iii) a mutual attitude of respect and open-mindedness, implying a willingness to learn and grow from the other, and (iv) significant religious content in, or implied by, the conversation.

Objectives of Interreligious Dialogue

The philosophers of religion and scholars of comparative religion have spelled out various aims and objectives of inter-religious dialogue, like (i) to know about other religions with a view to promoting diversity and pluralism; (ii) to ensure freedom of religion, which is the mother of all human rights, for “the degree to which freedom of religion is upheld reflects the general human rights situation in a particular country;”⁹ (iii) “to overcome renewed competition among religions and the fear that one religion is going to overtake the other;”¹⁰ and (iv) to stimulate discussion and to think about the challenges associated with the implementation and protection” of the the people’s right to freedom of religion and belief. The primary function of interreligious dialogue, however, should be a promotion of greater understanding between people of different religions and faiths. A sustained

8 Francis A. Arinze, *Meeting Other Believers*, Leominster: Gracewing Publishing, 1997, 67.

9 Piet De Klerk, *Nederland’s Ambassador to UN*. <https://news.bahai.org/story/405/> (accessed on March 30, 2024).

10 Asma Jahangir, *UNO Reporter on “Freedom of Religion.”* <https://www.onecountry.org/story/new-york-panelists-stress-importance-interreligious-dialogue> (accessed on March 20, 2024).

and scholarly discussion between representatives of religious groups will indeed clarify the areas of agreement and disagreement in beliefs and practices.

The effective dialogue, negatively speaking, enables participants to correctly identify areas of genuine religious disagreement, as well as identify misconceptions regarding the beliefs and practices of different religions. As Craig Bloomberg observes, in interreligious dialogue, “we recognize crucial issues that divide us; but for our conversations to be fruitful and honoring to God, we must stop misrepresenting, or caricaturing each other, always speaking the truth to each other in love.”¹¹ Positively speaking, the simplistic objective of interreligious dialogue would be to gain an understanding of the other religious traditions. For example, David Lochhead argues that “rather than defining dialogue as a search for agreement, it would be more helpful to define dialogue as a search for understanding.”¹²

At this juncture, it is worth stating the contribution of the Second Vatican Council (1962–1965) of the Catholic Church, which spoke emphatically on the role and significance of dialogue for fostering mutual appreciation and understanding among different religions and faiths. The Declaration *Nostra Aetate* exhorts the people of God “through dialogue and collaboration with the followers of other religions, [to] acknowledge, preserve, and promote the spiritual and moral goods found among these men, as well as the values in their society and culture.”¹³ Similarly, the Decree *Ad Gentes* instructs the disciples of Christ to “learn by sincere and patient dialogue what treasures a bountiful God has distributed among the nations of the earth.”¹⁴ In the words of Pope Francis, “Interreligious dialogue is a necessary condition for peace in the world, and so it is a duty for Christians as well as other religious communities.”¹⁵

11 Craig L. Blomberg, “Introduction” to *How Wide the Divide?* Downers Grove: InterVarsity, 1997, 27.

12 David Lochhead, *The Dialogical Imperative: A Christian Reflection on Interfaith Encounter*, Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 1988, 64.

13 *The Documents of Vatican II*, ed. Walter Abbot, USA: The America Press, 1966, *Nostra Aetate*, Art. 2.

14 *The Documents of Vatican II*, *Ad Gentes*, Art. 11.

15 Pope Francis, *Address during the Meeting with Academic and Cultural World*. Cagliari. September 22, 2013.

Types of Interreligious Dialogue

Indeed, interreligious dialogue is a very complex and many-faceted phenomenon. Hence, there can be no standard list of types of dialogue viewed from various factors that must be taken into consideration. The renowned scholar of Comparative Religion, Eric J. Sharpe, in his article “The Goals of Interreligious Dialogue,” classifies Interreligious Dialogue into four types: Human, Secular, Discursive, and Interior¹⁶. The Catholic Church offers a similar four-fold classification in the Dialogue and Proclamation: Dialogue of life, Dialogue of action, Theological dialogue, and Spiritual dialogue¹⁷.

a) Human Dialogue or Dialogue of life

Human dialogue is a form of interreligious dialogue that generally occurs at the most basic level. This kind of process, which involves social interaction in everyday activity, is also known as the “Dialogue of Life.” The Dialogue of Life is “where people strive to live in an open and neighborly spirit, sharing their joys and sorrows, their human problems and preoccupations.”¹⁸ This type of interreligious dialogue commonly occurs between interfaith communities at any place, when one encounters, lives, interacts with others, and participates together in day-to-day activities. These activities can be seen in the lives of interfaith families, celebrating festivities and wedding ceremonies, and doing business with other religious communities. What is specific about this form of dialogue is that it shows the involvement of non-elite participants in the interreligious dialogue at the grassroots level. Non-elite participation in interreligious dialogue is necessary to accommodate the challenges of today’s pluralistic society.

b) Secular Dialogue, or Collaborative Dialogue

Secular dialogue, or the Dialogue of Collaboration, involves people of different faiths

16 Eric J. Sharpe, “The Goals of Interreligious Dialogue,” in John Hick (ed.), *Truth and Dialogue in World Religions: Conflicting Truth-Claims*. Philadelphia: Westminster Press, 1974, 77-95.

17 Dialogue and Proclamation: Reflection and Orientations on Interreligious Dialogue and the Proclamation of the Gospel of Jesus Christ. Document of Pontifical Council for Interreligious Dialogue,” 1991, Art. 42. Cf. <https://www.vatican.va>.

18 Dialogue and Proclamation, 1991, Art. 42.

collaborating in matters of public/common concern. While relevant to such collaboration, religious beliefs are not discussed or brought into focus. Swain defines “Collaborative dialogue” as “dialogue in which speakers engage jointly in problem-solving and knowledge building.”¹⁹ Theoretically, collaborative dialogue can be about anything; however, in this paper, collaborative dialogue is applied to interfaith interaction, collaboration, and communication. Collaborative dialogues have been proposed in order to specifically focus on the role of dialogues and talk in learning situations. They can include dialogical teaching, exploratory talk, etc.

c) Discursive Dialogue, or Theological Dialogue

Discursive dialogue, or Theological dialogue, involves debate, scripture study, and such ‘scholarly’ endeavors. It is aimed at exploring another religion and trying to comprehend how it views these or those issues, and it often entails drawing a comparison with one’s own doctrine. Within the framework of the theological dialogue, “specialists seek to deepen their understanding of their respective religious heritages and to appreciate each other’s spiritual values.” Hence, the participants must be well informed about the theology, philosophy, beliefs, and customs of the two traditions involved.

d) Interior Dialogue, or Spiritual Dialogue

The Interior dialogue, or Spiritual dialogue, implies very close acquaintance with another religion, even to the extent of using its spiritual practices, and its goal is often seen as “mutual enrichment.” This kind of dialogue involves praying, meditating, fasting, etc., often involving the use of the spiritual methods of the other tradition. It can also involve praying together, each according to his/her own tradition or narrating/sharing one’s spiritual experiences. As the document Dialogue and Proclamation notes, within the framework of “the dialogue of religious experience [. . .] persons, rooted in their own religious traditions, share their spiritual riches, for instance with regard to prayer and contemplation, faith and ways of searching for

19 M. Swain, “The output hypothesis and beyond: Mediating acquisition through collaborative dialogue,” Lantolf J.P., ed. *Socio-cultural theory and second language learning*, Oxford: University Press, 2000, 102.

God or the Absolute.”

The above-mentioned four types of dialogue should ideally complement one another, for they are really interconnected. The contacts in a day-to-day life and common commitment to action will open the door for cooperation to promote human and spiritual values, which will eventually lead to the dialogue of religious experience.²⁰ However, if interreligious dialogue does not ultimately lead individuals to participate in Spiritual dialogue, it cannot attain its stated objective, namely comprehension of other religions in a ‘religious’ sense. As Wayne Teasdale argues, “All religious traditions emerge out of mystical experience [foundational experience]. One can say that the real religion of humankind isn’t religion at all; rather, it is mystical spirituality, the bosom out of which the religions themselves have been born.”²¹

Are there boundaries between different religions?

Scholars and philosophers of religion are divided on the question of whether there are boundaries between different religions and faiths. A group of thinkers, like William James, hold the view that there are no boundaries among religions of the world. On the contrary, philosophers like David Hume argue that there are boundaries between religions.

Some thinkers argue that one could very well conceive of religious experience as a whole without cuts and breaks, like “a stream of consciousness.” For instance, William James, in “Essays in Radical Empiricism,” speaks of “pure experience,” which is devoid of all distinctions and qualifications (“neutral monism”)²². On James’ theory, pure experience is “indescribable and formless,”²³ but language, being a schematism, cannot report it in its formlessness. It is beyond doubt that something is wrong with such a view of religious experience because it contradicts empirical evidence. For William James, distinctions

are introduced to discriminate “functions” within pure experience; they signify different “ways” in which experience may be taken. James follows and departs from David Hume: James says of his philosophy: “It is essentially a mosaic philosophy, a philosophy of plural facts, like that of Hume.”²⁴ James, however, could not accept Hume’s main thesis: “All our distinct perceptions are distinct existences, [and] the mind never perceives any real connection among distinct existences.”²⁵

If our experiences are really “distinct and no connection” whatsoever exists among them, then our attempt at interreligious dialogue would be futile and meaningless. On the contrary, if we stretch James’ argument of “neutral monism” too much, we would have no right to use expressions/concepts like Christianity, Islam, Judaism, Hinduism, etc. Hence, what is advocated is James’ generalized conclusion that “the parts of experience hold together next by next by relations that are themselves parts of experience.”²⁶ What experience delivers is not exhausted by “atomic elements”, characterized by disjunctions, but it necessarily contains conjunctions requisite for whatever unity and continuity it exhibits within itself. It may thus be concluded that if the disjunctive relations can be accepted as real on the basis of empirical evidence, the conjunctive relations, which are equally revealed in experience, can also be accepted as real. Such a radical empiricist view of experience thus provides sufficient scope for dialogue and sharing of religious experiences by people of different religions and faiths.

Search for Paradigms in Interreligious Dialogue

Thomas Kuhn, a practicing historian of science, emphasizes the critical role of paradigms, which are taken to be “universally recognized scientific achievements that for a time provide model problems and solutions to a community of practitioners.”²⁷ According to Kuhn, science

20 Cf. The Documents of Vatican II, *Nostra Aetate*, Art. 2.

21 Wayne Teasdale, “Mysticism as the Crossing of Ultimate Boundaries,” *Frontier Violations*, ed. Felix Wilfred, New York: Orbis Books, 1999, 91.

22 William James, *Essays in Radical Empiricism*, ed. Ralph Perry, Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1996, 4-5.

23 William James, *Essays in Radical Empiricism*, 46.

24 William James, *Essays in Radical Empiricism*, 42.

25 David Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, ed. L.A. Selby-Bigge, Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1978, 636.

26 William James, *The Meaning of Truth*, Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1978, 6-7.

27 Thomas Kuhn, *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1970, viii.

goes through a “paradigm shift” when current theories cannot explain some phenomenon, and someone proposes a new theory. A paradigm shift occurs when the new paradigm explains better the observations and is offering a model that is closer to the objective external reality. The new paradigm is incommensurate with the old. In the research tradition, a paradigm-as-exemplar fulfills three functions: “(i) it suggests new puzzles (questions), (ii) it suggests approaches to solving those puzzles, (iii) it is the standard by which the quality of a proposed puzzle-solution can be measured.”²⁸

True to the spirit of research tradition, various paradigms, and method models have been proposed and practiced down through the centuries in interreligious dialogue. Some of the well-known and tested models are (i) the ideal of both/and (Fichte and Hegel), (ii) the ideal of either/or (Kierkegaard), (iii) the metaphor of two books (Bonaventure), (iv) the intercultural hermeneutics (Schleiermacher and Gadamer), and (v) the fusion of horizons (Heidegger and Gadamer).

a) The Ideal of “Both/And”

The dialectic method, introduced by Plato and Aristotle, was first presented in the triadic form by Johann G. Fichte, consisting of thesis, antithesis, and synthesis.²⁹ For G.W.F. Hegel, who accepted Fichte’s triad, reality at all levels exemplifies an unending dialectic process. In the Hegelian dialectic, one begins by offering two seemingly opposite ideas and then arrives at a synthesis of them, which merges the two into a new understanding. The simplest explanation of Hegelian dialectic is this: an argument (thesis) is proposed, generating a counterargument (the antithesis), and, much like in the scientific method, philosophers take the merits of both the thesis and antithesis into account, creating a new thesis called the synthesis. Hegel, for instance, sought to reconcile oppositions (Sein an-sich and Sein für-sich) and to integrate opposite ends of the spectrum into a synthesis (Sein an-und-für-sich), which would blunt either extreme.

Dialectical models of dialogue have

²⁸ Thomas Kuhn, *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*, 38-39.

²⁹ Cf. Christian Klotz, “Fichte’s Explanation of the Dynamic Structure of Consciousness in the 1794-95 *Wissenschaftslehre*,” in *The Cambridge Companion to Fichte*, ed. David James, Cambridge: University Printing Press, 2016, 72-73.

both advantages and disadvantages. One of the advantages of these models is that they provide a formal and normative framework for deliberation, which is useful in dialogue and decision-making processes. Moreover, they offer a structured approach to argumentation and can support systems in problem-solving and decision-making. They emphasize the commonality of human experiences of the partners in dialogue, based on a minimum common program, striving toward the common good of all.

On the other hand, synthesis as a complete merging of every bit of experience with every other bit, or as a ‘through-and-through’ type of union, is not an acceptable model for interreligious dialogue. Critics argue that dialectical models may overemphasize the epistemic facet of decision-making and fail to consider other important aspects, such as respect for individual charism and judgment. In his article “The Politics of Recognition,” Charles Taylor also argues that it is important to recognize identity and difference, especially in a multi-religious context. Taylor contends that “our identity is shaped by recognition or its absence.”³⁰ Hence due recognition and acceptance is not merely a courtesy but a vital human need. Recognition of identity also leads to respect for differences. Recognizing differences between individuals or groups means paying attention to them and respecting them simply because they are specific aspects of a shared identity.

Indeed, it is vital to recognize identity and difference, especially in a multi-religious context. However, all the more important is the self-awareness that identity and difference are created dialogically, i.e., in response to our relations, including our actual dialogues with others. This dialogue invites us “to go beyond barriers and meet others as subjects, as people sharing the same territory.”³¹ It is by emphasizing the dialogical aspect that recognition comes into full significance.

b) The Ideal of “Either Or”

Soren Kierkegaard, initially fascinated by

³⁰ Charles Taylor, “The Politics of Recognition,” in Amy Gutmann, ed., *Multiculturalism: Examining the Politics of Recognition*, New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 1994, 25.

³¹ Jacques Audinet, *The Human Face of Globalization*, trans. Francis Dal Chele, Lanham: Rowman, 1999, 29.

the Hegelian dialectic, eventually discarded it. Kierkegaard's basic outlook is a very antithesis of Hegel's, who sought to reconcile the oppositions (Sein an-sich and Sein für-sich). On the contrary, Kierkegaard called for a clear-cut radical commitment: Either/Or.³² A common interpretation of Either/Or presents the people with a choice between two approaches to religion and religious experience.

The ideal of 'Either Or' does not, in any way, help us in interreligious dialogue. Rather, it paves the way for exclusiveness, leading to conflicts and struggles over truth claims. Some of the unfortunate consequences of this model are fundamentalism and/or fanaticism, leading to violence and bloodshed (for example, the Crusades). One of the major threats to the model of Either/Or in interreligious dialogue is 'ethnocentrism.' Ethnocentrism is the attitude that one's own group, ethnicity, or religion is superior to others.³³ Ethnocentric individuals, accordingly, judge other groups relative to their own ethnic group, especially with concern for language, behavior, customs, and religion.

c) Alternative Models in Interreligious Dialogue

These alternative models aim neither at a 'total inclusion' (both/and) nor a 'total exclusion' (either/or), but an interplay of the plurality of religious experiences. This dual-mode approach to religious experience gave rise to the well-known "metaphor of two books" - the Book of Scripture and the Book of Nature- which was very popular in the Middle Ages and the early modern period. According to Saint Bonaventure, the same God expresses his will in and through "the Book of Scripture" and "the Book of Nature."³⁴ That is to say, although the language used in the two books is different, the speaker/author is one and the same.

Likewise, Russell and Frege claim that the same reference can be presented in different ways and via different modes of presentation. Russell's classic example of this point concerns 'Sir Walter

Scott' and 'the author of Waverley.'³⁵ "If we say 'Scott is the author of Waverley,' we assert an identity of denotation with a difference of meaning."³⁶ The two expressions - 'Sir Walter Scott' and 'the author of Waverley'- do not have the same meaning, although they refer to the same individual since Scott is the author of Waverley. Frege's famous example is that of the "morning star" and the "evening star," which have the same referent, namely the planet Venus, although the meanings are different.³⁷ For, the morning star means 'the celestial object visible in the morning sky just before sunrise', whereas the evening star means 'the celestial object visible in the evening sky just after sunset'. All the same, to say 'Venus is Venus' is simply a tautology, whereas the 'morning star' is the 'evening star' is not a tautology, although both terms have the same referent, Venus.

Russell and Frege seem to suggest that the modes of presentation may be different, yet the ones represented could be the same. Unlike 'both/and' and 'either/or', this model suggests an interplay of the plurality of religious experiences. By way of application, we can reason out that the different religions are "different modes of presentation or experience of reality," yet they could refer to the same reality (the Divine, the Ineffable, etc.).

Fusion of Horizons

Now, we focus on the possibility of a genuine interreligious dialogue according to Gadamer's notion of the "fusion of horizons." Gadamer states that the human being is blessed with the ability to understand, and understanding is modeled on the act of 'conversation' in which we engage with others. The fact that different points of view of dialogue-partners are merging in the process of understanding, leading them to a better and mutual understanding, hence, a "fusion of horizons." According to Georgia Warnke, a 'fusion of horizons' in Gadamer's writings is understood in a two-fold sense: "[...] on the one hand, we understand the object (for example, religious tradition) from the point of view of our assumptions and situation; on the other, our final perspective reflects the

32 Soren Kierkegaard, *Either Or: A fragment of Life*, ed., Victor Eremita, New York: Penguin Classics, 1843

33 Cf. Fay Patel, *Overview of Intercultural Communication*, New Delhi: Sage Publication, 2011, 33.

34 J. Guy Bougerol, *Introduction to The Works of Bonaventure*, New Jersey: St. Anthony Guild Press, 1964, 78.

35 Bertrand Russell, *Principia Mathematica*, London: George Allen & Unwin, 1925-27, 191.

36 Bertrand Russell, "On Denoting," *Mind*, 14 (1905), 489.

37 Gottlob Frege, *Logical Investigations*, ed., Peter Geach, New Haven: Yale University Press, 1977, 27.

education we have received through our encounter with the object,"³⁸ and such a fusion helps us integrate certain points of view, and advance to a new understanding of the issues in question.

Accordingly, Gadamer describes a "horizon" as 'the totality of all that can be realized or thought about, by a person at a given time in history and in a particular culture. "To acquire a "horizon" means that one learns to look beyond what is close at hand – not in order to look away from it but to see it better with a larger whole and truer proportion."³⁹ In the hermeneutical philosophy of Gadamer, a "fusion of horizons" (Horizontverschmelzung) is the process through which the members of a hermeneutical dialogue establish the broader context within which they come to a shared understanding.

For Gadamer, we exist neither in closed horizons nor within a horizon that is unique. We must reject both the assumption of absolute knowledge, that universal history can be articulated within a single horizon, and the assumption of objectivity, that we can "forget ourselves" to achieve the other participant's objective perspective. To gain an understanding from a dialogue about different religions, Gadamer argues, we must acquire the right horizon of inquiry for the questions evoked by the encounter through negotiation; to come to an agreement, the participants must establish a shared context through this 'fusion' of their horizons.

Some of the critics of Gadamer think that the "fusion" is opposed to differences among viewpoints because it tries to force 'two' into 'one', and so it does away with a diversity of perspectives. For example, Derrida argues that understanding as a fusion of horizons ignores the otherness of the other by homogenizing the different points of view. Suppressing the otherness of the other cannot thus be ethical.⁴⁰ Additionally, Habermas sees Gadamer's notion of the "fusion of horizons" as a kind of unification that involves the submission of one horizon to another: "[...] the popular phrase 'fusion of horizons' is commonly interpreted and criticized as meaning the submission of one horizon to

another, where the outcome is either a dominating past or dominating present."⁴¹ These critics of Gadamer's notion of understanding as a fusion of horizons point to a potential problem when we endeavor to develop a shared understanding.

To overcome this potential problem, Erdal Yilmaz explores Gadamer's notion of understanding as a fusion of horizons based on his analysis of the concepts of "dialogue" and "play" (Spiel)⁴². Understanding, conceived as "play," reveals an interplay" (Ineinanderspiel); a dynamic, ongoing "sharing" of a common game. In the back-and-forth movement of the interplay, the different points of view are not eliminated by the domination of one's own claims of truth onto that of the other, but superseded by a larger truth that belongs to neither one nor the other. A genuine fusion of horizons through dialogue always entails achieving a higher universality that transcends both our own and the other person's particularity.⁴³ In the Gadamerian model, treating the other as a 'play partner' does not entail suppressing difference but demands the partners' respect and preserve the diversity between them.

A fusion of horizons thus envisages respect for the differences of different religions. Here, one does not try to acquire mastery over the other and other religions based on our pre-judgments but rather strives to partake in the other, to share the other's alterity. Moreover, for Gadamer, the ongoing play process of understanding never ceases, and so common understanding continues to be improved. For this reason, the partner will not reach the final state of absolute knowledge, where they agree about everything once and for all. Every agreement causes new disagreements in the ongoing play process of dialogue. Gadamer's notion of the fusion of horizons thus has a dynamic process, and this process requires an 'openness' of the participants with one another, leading their encounter toward a genuine interreligious dialogue.

41 Habermas, J. "A Review of Gadamer's Truth and Method," in *The Hermeneutic Tradition*, ed., G. L. Ormiston and A. D. Shrift, Albany: State University of New York, 1990, 236.

42 Erdal Yilmaz, "The fusion of horizons: The possibility of a genuine ethical dialogue," *South African Journal of Philosophy*, 2022, 41/3, 229–239.

43 Jos de Mull, "Horizons of Hermeneutics," *Frontiers of Philosophy in China* 6/3 (2011), 640.

Furthermore, a genuine dialogue focused on the other involves a willingness to put oneself and one's traditions, or the fragments of a tradition, at risk. "To risk oneself in dialogue" does not mean to enter with either a lack of self-respect or a lack of knowledge of and affirmation of at least the most important events of one's traditions.⁴⁴ That is to say, one enters a dialogue with one's critical consciousness vigilant and with a knowledge and respect for one's own traditions. Only in that manner does one fully enter into dialogue, into the 'to' and 'fro' movement of the peculiar question and response at issue in the subject matter under question. For genuine dialogue, one must learn ever anew the skills to play well, as in any game.

Finally, to foster interreligious dialogue as a "fusion of horizons, we have to cultivate certain essential qualities like, (a) openness to change, (b) interreligious consciousness, and (c) empathetic understanding.

Openness to Change

Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics states, "a person trying to understand a tradition (religion) is prepared for it to tell him something."⁴⁵ Though a person approaches the tradition (religion) with his own prejudices, these prejudices should be open to change to have a better relationship with the tradition (religion). Now, in the inter-religious context, this openness is necessary for the one who engages in an interreligious dialogue. Every person who comes in contact with other religions would be always looking at them from one's own context. This context of one's own religion is what forms the fore-understanding in every person. It is important, therefore, that one is able to be open to change and enhance this fore-understanding to have a positive relation with other religions. In other words, dialogue demands of us a truly contemplative spirit of openness and receptivity to the other. "I cannot engage in dialogue, if I am closed to others. Openness? Even more: acceptance! Come to my house, enter my heart. My heart welcomes you. It wants to hear you."⁴⁶

44 Cf. David Tracy, "Western Hermeneutics and Inter-Religious Dialogue," in *Fragments*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2020.

45 Georg Gadamer, *Truth and Method*, 269.

46 Pope Francis, "Address to Bishops of Asia," August 17, 2014.

a) *Inter-religious Consciousness*

India is a land that has a long, heterogeneous religious and cultural background and a richly diverse history. This is the idea of India that suits well to its name. Therefore, "this idea of India should be militated against a religiously, or culturally, separatist view. This is possible only through the development of an inter-religious, intercultural hermeneutical consciousness. When dealing with the interpretation of a text Gadamer says "a hermeneutically trained consciousness must be, from the start, sensitive to the text's alterity."⁴⁷ If this is applied in an interreligious situation, when someone wants to enter into a dialogue with another religion, he should also develop an inter-religious hermeneutical consciousness. The reason is that "all religions have a specific context; they may be open to outside influence, but cannot be substituted with another, and if any such attempt is made, the result would be tragic."⁴⁸ Only that person, who is conscious of inter-religious situations and the need for a hermeneutical approach to understand the very essence of a particular religion from its own context will be successful in relating positively with other religions. Inter-religious hermeneutics is aimed at recognizing and respecting the distinctive characteristics of each religion by not superimposing oneself on the other but by accepting the distinctions among the religions. It is an inevitable fact that different religions exist together, and a better attitude in this plurality is "to celebrate the diversity' (differences), yet enjoy the unity (togetherness).

b) *Empathetic Understanding*

In order to recognize and celebrate the difference and enjoy togetherness, we need to develop another interrelation quality, namely "empathy." As we know, each religion is different and has evolved differently. Even in today's global village, these diversities are seen vividly. In what appears to be an increasingly similar world, "there is a continued miracle of diversity and differences,

https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/speeches/2014/august/documents/papa-francesco_20140817_corea-vescovi-asia.html (accessed on 17 April 2024).

47 Georg Gadamer, *Truth and Method*, 269.

48 Pavan Varma, *Becoming Indian: The Unfinished Revolution of Culture and Identity*, New Delhi: Penguin Books India Private Ltd., 2010, 239.

often impatient to be recognized.”⁴⁹ To the centrality of diversity and differences, Pope Francis adds empathy as a basic attitude for making the process of dialogue more effective.

Empathy is transposing ourselves to other’s situation in our attempt to understand the situation of the other better. Gadamer insists that “if we put ourselves in someone else’s shoes, then we will understand him – i.e., become aware of the otherness, the indissoluble individuality of the other person – by putting ourselves in his position.”⁵⁰ As suggested by Frederick Whaling, it is necessary to try to know the other’s religion, or culture, by penetrating the sense of what it means for that other to be a Hindu, Muslim, or Buddhist. It is a matter of looking at the world from the other’s viewpoint.⁵¹ Pope Francis explained this process in a most effective form in the course of a speech addressed to the Asian bishops in Seoul: “For dialogue to take place there has to be this empathy. We are challenged to listen not only to the words that others speak but also to the unspoken communication of their experiences, hopes and aspirations, struggles, and deepest concerns. Such empathy must [...] lead us to see others as brothers and sisters, and to ‘hear’, in and beyond their words and actions, what their hearts wish to communicate.”⁵²

In fact, the climax of true empathy is to understand fully the suffering and pain of the other as my own. Finally, an empathic approach enables a truly human dialogue in which words, ideas, and questions arise from an experience of fraternity and shared humanity.

In empathy, we do not let go of our own selves; rather, we carry ourselves into the other. In Pope Francis’ view, the preservation of one’s own identity is the condition for offering the ‘other’ the uniqueness that one has and, at the same time, for accepting the other as a gift. This process requires an attitude of openness facilitated by the effort to fully understand the other side. Here lies the value of empathy that allows each partner involved

49 Pavan Varma, *Becoming Indian: The Unfinished Revolution of Culture and Identity*, 250.

50 Georg Gadamer, *Truth and Method*, 305.

51 Whaling, Frederick, *Christian Theology and World Religions: A Global Approach*, Basingstoke: Marshall Pickering, 1986. 130-131.

52 Pope Francis, “Address to Bishops of Asia,” August 17, 2014. <https://www.vatican.va>.

in dialogue to open up to the other while fully welcoming his or her way of thinking, believing, and living. Interreligious dialogue is ultimately rooted on the conviction that there is much within all religions and cultures that can provide the foundation for a global edifice of dialogue and harmony.

Conclusion

When sincerely attempted, interreligious dialogue usually leads to a more harmonious relationship between the various religious traditions. “Sincerity” is a key qualifier, essential to retain the spirit of dialogue. It is this sincerity that leads to true tolerance. A polite glossing over of differences between religious traditions, or a mushy oversimplification of the core issues with superficial statements, like “It’s all one God” is antithetical to the spirit of dialogue. Hence, the call for interreligious dialogue is an appeal to those who believe in constructing rather than destroying; to those who embrace diversity as a means of progress and achievement rather than as a threat; and to those who believe in the dignity of the humans rather than the superiority of some or other sections of humanity.

To successfully engage in the dialogue of life with people of other faith traditions, one has to genuinely love them and desire a good neighborly relationship with them. Similarly, a compassionate disposition is indispensable to promoting just cause and bringing liberation (dialogue of action) to the less privileged in society. Thus, imbibing a strong sense of love and compassion, people living in religiously pluralistic societies will be able to engage in meaningful dialogue of life and dialogue of action (i) to promote better relationships and respect for each other and (ii) to collaborate with each other to achieve noble goals for the common good, namely “for the integral development and liberation of people.”⁵³ In the words of His Holiness Pope St. John Paul II, I conclude with a prayer: “In the Interreligious dialogue, we may trace a journey which has led humanity down the centuries to meet and engage truth more and more deeply.”⁵⁴

53 *Dialogue and Proclamation*, Pontifical Council for Interreligious Dialogue, 1991, Art. 42.

54 St. John Paul II, *Fides et Ratio*, Vatican City: Libreria Editrice Vaticana, 1998, Art. 1.